

Stoichiometry-controlled supramolecular chirality induction in magnesium(II) porphyrin dimer by amino alcohols : Mechanistic insights and effect of ligand bulkiness[†]

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Abstract : The rationalization of the chirality induction mechanism between an achiral and highly flexible Mg^{II}-1,2-bis(*meso*-octaethylporphyrin)ethane as a host and a series of chiral amino alcohol as guest has been studied here which results in the formation of 1 : 1 (*sandwich*) and 1 : 2 host-guest (*anti*) complexes at the guest's low and high concentration regions, respectively. Large CD amplitude for the 1 : 1 *sandwich* complex is observed due to very strong binding of the guest within the bisporphyrin host which has also been increased with the increasing bulk of the substituent at the stereogenic centre. Single crystal X-ray structure of two such 1 : 2 *anti* complexes are reported here in which the guest ligations occur from the side that result in a close spatial proximity to the ethyl groups of the adjacent porphyrin and thereby leading to a stereospecific twist of the two bridged porphyrin units either in a clockwise or anti-clockwise direction in order to minimize the host-guest steric clash. The pre-existing chirality of the amino alcohol guests would make the two porphyrin macrocycles to be oriented in a clockwise direction for *S*-type of chiral guest while anticlockwise for an *R*-type of guest which results in the positive and negative sign of the first Cotton effect of the CD couplet that are also observed experimentally.

Keywords : Mg^{II}-bisporphyrin, molecular switching, *sandwich* complex, *anti* complex, circular dichroism, binding constant, structure elucidation.

Introduction

Supramolecular chirogenesis is a modern interdisciplinary field of research that deals with asymmetry information transfer within multimolecular systems via noncovalent interactions. Since chiral supramolecular sensing event is directly dependent on any part or whole of the multicomponent assembly, it has broad range of applications in molecular sciences. This intriguing phenomenon is vastly abundant in many natural such as the DNA double helix, secondary *R*-helix structure of proteins as well as various artificial systems. Thus supramolecular chirogenesis is highly important in fundamental science, with practical applications in materials and polymer sciences, chiral memory, enantioselective catalysis, chiral switch, nonlinear optics, *etc.*¹⁻⁴. Therefore, a detailed understanding of the underpinning mechanisms and various influencing factors of supramolecular science is of prime importance.

Porphyrinoids have been shown to be well suited for investigating the processes involved in supramolecular chirality induction owing to their interesting photophysical properties, versatile modification, great biological importance, and wide applicability⁴⁻¹⁰. There is a vast literature reports of supramolecular complexes containing metalloporphyrin as host and chiral/achiral substrate as guest through axial ligation⁴⁻¹¹. Achiral bisporphyrin receptors are used as powerful tools for the absolute configurational analysis of organic compounds using CD spectroscopy. Generation of chirality within the supramolecular complex is occurred due to the stereospecific twisting of the two bridged porphyrin units, caused by the enantiomerically pure chiral substrates in order to minimize the host-guest steric clash. The complex exhibits an exciton couplet in the porphyrin Soret band region of the circular dichroism (CD) spectrum, whose sign is governed by the absolute

[†]In honour of Professor Animesh Chakravorty on the occasion of his 80th birth anniversary.

configuration of the guest, while its amplitude depends on various external (i.e. temperature, pH and polarity of the medium, etc.) and internal factors (i.e. bond strength, stoichiometry, electronic effects, etc.). Substrates' pre-organized coordinating sites along with the differences in the effective size of the substituent around the chiral center dictate the sign of the interporphyrin helical twist.

Ethane bridged Mg^{II}-bisporphyrin has been used as an effective achiral host here. A large number of dihememes and related complexes have been investigated using such a flexible ethane bridged bisporphyrin as a part of our ongoing research activities¹². In the present work, however, we investigate the effect of stoichiometry on the chirality induction process using highly flexible achiral Mg^{II}-bisporphyrin host with chiral amino alcohol guests in the host-guest supramolecular complex. Chirality inductions with bifunctional guests have been found to occur via stepwise 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 host-guest complexation processes. Also, only a few reports^{10b,13} are there for the chirality induction process using Mg^{II} as a metal ion which strongly binds through the alcoholic oxygen only. We report here the synthesis, structure and spectroscopic properties of a series of supramolecular chiral 1 : 1 *sandwich* and 1 : 2 *anti* complexes using a variety of chiral amino alcohol guests. The bulk of the substituent at the stereogenic center has been varied successively in order to specify the role played by the steric differentiation at the chiral center in the overall helicity of the complex. Crystallographic and other spectroscopic investigation of the complexes enable us to rationalize the origin of the optical activity unambiguously in the supramolecular host-guest complexes at the molecular levels. The present investigation will also allow comparing and correlating the chirality induction process with the nature of supramolecular host for absolute stereochemical determination. Single crystal X-ray structures of the *anti* form in a Mg^{II}-bisporphyrin induced by the axial ligand is reported here which shows inside binding of the chiral ligand and thereby induces chirality in the complex. These systematic studies will lead to the development of an efficient chirality sensor for various classes of chiral compounds and will open up further perspectives for the design of smart chiroptical devices.

Experimental

Materials :

1,2-Bis(*meso*-octaethylporphyrinyl)ethane, and its Mg-

complex, **1**, are prepared by the literature methods¹³. Reagents and solvents are purchased from commercial sources and purified by standard procedures before use.

1 : 1 *sandwich* complexes reported in the present work were prepared using the general procedure; details for one representative case have been described below.

Synthesis of sandwich-1•(2_G) :

Mg^{II}-bisporphyrin **1** (50 mg, 0.043 mmol) was dissolved in 3 mL of distilled dichloromethane. (*S*)-2-Aminopropan-1-ol (**2_G**) (6 mg, 0.08 mmol) was then added to it and stirred for 10 min. After filtration to remove the solid residue, the solution was carefully layered in air with acetonitrile at room temperature. Dark crystalline solid of the complex were precipitated out after 6–8 days which was then isolated by filtration, washed well with hexane and dried in vacuum. (Yield 36 mg, 68%); UV-Vis (chloroform) [λ_{\max} , nm (ϵ , M⁻¹ cm⁻¹)] : 406 (2.75 × 10⁵), 414 (2.94 × 10⁵), 557 (2.75 × 10⁴), 603 (2.36 × 10⁴); ESI-MS : *m/z* 1214.7849 ([M+H]⁺); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 295 K) δ : 9.86 (2H, s, 10-*meso-H*), 9.37 (2H, s, 15-*meso-H*), 8.72 (2H, s, 20-*meso-H*), 6.65 (2H, s, -CH₂(b)), 6.05 (2H, d, -CH₂(b)), 4.27–3.05 (32H, m, -CH₂CH₃), 2.42–0.53 (48H, m, -CH₃), -0.8 (2H, br, -CH₃(L)), -1.3 (H, br, -CH(L)), -2.3 (2H, br, -CH₂(L)), -4.5 (3H, br, -NH₂, -OH(L)).

Sandwich-1•(3_G) : Yield 34 mg, 62%; UV-Vis (chloroform) [λ_{\max} , nm (ϵ , M⁻¹ cm⁻¹)] : 407 (2.73 × 10⁵), 415 (2.90 × 10⁵), 558 (2.76 × 10⁴), 603 (2.44 × 10⁴); ESI-MS : *m/z* 1229.8052 ([M+2H]⁺), ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 295 K) δ : 9.95 (2H, s, 10-*meso-H*), 9.37 (2H, s, 15-*meso-H*), 8.68 (2H, s, 20-*meso-H*), 6.70 (2H, s, -CH₂(b)), 6.08 (2H, d, -CH₂(b)), 4.32–3.15 (32H, m, -CH₂CH₃), 2.46–0.45 (48H, m, -CH₃), -1.2 (3H, br, -CH₃(L)), -2.0 (2H, br, -CH₂(L)), -3.6 (H, br, -CH(L)), -5.2 (2H, br, -CH₂(L)), -7.5 (3H, br, -NH₂, -OH(L)).

Sandwich-1•(4_G) : Yield 32 mg, 52%; UV-Vis (chloroform) [λ_{\max} , nm (ϵ , M⁻¹ cm⁻¹)] : 406 (2.7 × 10⁵), 414 (2.92 × 10⁵), 557 (2.8 × 10⁴), 603 (2.4 × 10⁴); ESI-MS : *m/z* 1289.7939 ([M]⁺); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 295 K) δ : 9.95 (2H, s, 10-*meso-H*), 9.45 (2H, s, 15-*meso-H*), 8.65 (2H, s, 20-*meso-H*), 6.80 (5H, br, -CH, Ph(L)), 6.62 (2H, d, -CH₂(b)), 6.23 (2H, d, -CH₂(b)), 4.36–3.25 (32H, m, -CH₂CH₃), 2.25–0.65 (48H, m, -CH₃), -3.7 (2H, br, -CH₂(L)), -4.2 (2H, br, -CH₂(L)), -5.1 (2H, br, -CH₂(L)), -7.2 (3H, br, -NH₂, -OH(L)).

Sandwich-1•(5)_S : Yield 28 mg, 67%; UV-Vis (chloroform) [λ_{max} , nm (ϵ , $\text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)] : 407 (2.68×10^5), 415 (2.85×10^5), 558 (2.83×10^4), 603 (2.45×10^4); ESI-MS : m/z 1277.8052 ($[\text{M}+2\text{H}]^+$); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 295 K) δ : 9.92 (2H, s, 10-meso-*H*), 9.46 (2H, s, 15-meso-*H*), 8.73 (2H, s, 20-meso-*H*), 6.85 (5H, br, -*CH*, Ph(L)), 6.65 (2H, d, - $\text{CH}_2(\text{b})$), 6.15 (2H, d, - $\text{CH}_2(\text{b})$), 4.33–3.22 (32H, m, - CH_2CH_3), 2.21–0.72 (48H, m, - CH_3), -0.8 (1H, br, -*CH*(L)), -1.5 (2H, s, - $\text{CH}_2(\text{L})$), -2.4 (3H, br, - NH_2 , -*OH*(L)).

Anti-1•(6)₂ : Yield 25 mg, 64%; UV-Vis (chloroform) [λ_{max} , nm (ϵ , $\text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)] : 421 (2.53×10^5), 438 (2.32×10^5), 563 (2.72×10^4), 604 (2.41×10^4); ESI-MS : m/z 1318.8612 ($[\text{M}+2\text{H}]^+$); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 295 K) δ : 9.54 (2H, s, 15-meso-*H*), 9.35 (4H, s, 10,20-meso-*H*), 6.10 (4H, br, - $\text{CH}_2(\text{b})$), 4.32–3.46 (32H, m, - CH_2CH_3), 2.24–0.62 (48H, m, - CH_3), -0.92 (6H, br, - $\text{CH}_3(\text{L})$), -1.10 (2H, s, - $\text{CH}_2(\text{L})$), -2.56 (3H, br, - NH_2 , -*OH*(L)).

Instrumentation :

UV-Vis and CD-spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer UV-Vis and a JASCO J-815 spectrometer, respectively. ESI-MS spectra were recorded on a waters Micromass Quattro Micro triple quadrupole mass spectrometer. Isotopic pattern simulations are done by the software “Isotope Pattern Calculator v4.0” developed by Junhua Yan 2001.9. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on a JEOL 500 MHz instrument. The residual ^1H resonances of the solvents were used as a secondary reference.

DFT and TDDFT calculations :

DFT calculations have been carried out B3LYP¹⁴ functional using Gaussian 09, revision B.01 package¹⁵. The basis set was 6-31G+(d,p) for carbon, nitrogen, oxygen and hydrogen atoms. Geometry optimizations were carried out taking coordinates from previously reported Zn-bisporphyrin analogue. TDDFT method is used to calculate excitation energies and rotational strength in order to obtain calculated CD spectra. Processing of the TD calculations and comparison with the experimental spectra was done with SpecDis¹⁶. The following CD shifts and σ values were used : 15 nm and 0.07 eV for **3_S**, 18 nm and 0.08 eV for **3_R**.

X-Ray structure solution and refinement :

Crystals were coated with light hydrocarbon oil and

mounted in the 100 K dinitrogen stream of Bruker SMART APEX CCD diffractometer equipped with CRYO Industries low-temperature apparatus and intensity data were collected using graphite-monochromated Mo K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$). The data integration and reduction were processed with SAINT software¹⁷. An absorption correction was applied¹⁸. Structures were solved by the direct method using SHELXS-97 and were refined on F² by full-matrix least-squares technique using the SHELXL-2014 program package¹⁹. Non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically. In the refinement, hydrogens were treated as riding atoms using SHELXL default parameters. Crystal data and data collection parameters for the complexes are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Crystal data and data collection parameters for the complexes

	<i>anti-1•(4)_S</i> ₂	<i>anti-1•(6)₂</i>
<i>T</i> (K)	100(2)	100(2)
Formula	C ₉₂ H ₁₁₆ Mg ₂ N ₁₀ O ₂	C ₈₄ H ₁₁₂ C ₁₆ Mg ₂ N ₁₀ O ₂
Formula weight	1442.56	1555.15
Color	Red	Red
Crystal system	Triclinic	Monoclinic
Space group	<i>P</i> -1	<i>P</i> ₂ ₁ / <i>n</i>
<i>a</i> (Å)	11.909(5)	12.426(4)
<i>b</i> (Å)	13.787(5)	21.490(6)
<i>c</i> (Å)	14.508(5)	16.588(5)
α (deg)	62.637(5)	90
β (deg)	70.139(5)	110.237(6)
γ (deg)	89.979(5)	90
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	1954.8(13)	4156(2)
Radiation (λ , Å)	Mo K α (0.71073)	Mo K α (0.71073)
<i>Z</i>	1	2
<i>d</i> _{calcd.} (g•cm ⁻³)	1.225	1.243
μ (mm ⁻¹)	0.088	0.274
<i>F</i> (000)	778	1656
No. of unique data	6718	7300
No. of restraints	1	2
No. of params. refined	511	576
GOF on F ²	1.139	1.065
R1 ^a [<i>I</i> > 2 σ (<i>I</i>)]	0.0928	0.0952
R1 ^a (all data)	0.1111	0.1249
wR2 ^b (all data)	0.2282	0.2768

$${}^a\text{R1} = \frac{\sum \|F_0\| - \|F_c\|}{\sum \|F_0\|}, \quad {}^b\text{WR}^2 = \sqrt{\frac{\sum [w(F_0^2 - F_c^2)^2]}{\sum [w(F_0^2)^2]}}$$

Results and discussion

Mg^{II}-1,2-bis(*meso*-octaethylporphyrinyl)ethane, **1**, was prepared using the procedure reported earlier.

1 : 1 complexation in solution at the lower ligand concentration (Fig. 3).

Upon further increase of host : guest molar ratio from

Scheme 1

The stepwise addition of amino alcohol L as a guest ligand to **1** produces large change in the UV-Vis spectra; Fig. 1 demonstrates the spectral changes in dichloromethane upon gradual addition of (*S*)-2-amino-3-phenylpropan-1-ol (**4_S**) as a representative example. As can be seen, the intensity of the Soret band at 406 and 414 nm decreases while a shoulder peak at 434 nm slowly grows with increasing **4_S** concentration that varies from host : guest molar ratio of 1 : 0.1 to 1 : 660. During such process, small increments in the Q-band intensities also occur at 557 and 601 nm. The complex has been isolated as solid in good yield and spectroscopically characterized as 1 : 1 *sandwich-1·4_S*. ESI mass spectral analysis has revealed a signal at *m/z* 1289.7939 confirming the formation of such complex. The isotopic distribution pattern of the experimental mass was matching exactly with the theoretical pattern (Fig. 2). Job's continuous variation plot was done based on CD spectral titrations, which also confirms the

Fig. 1. UV-Vis spectral changes (selected portions only) of **1** ($5 \times 10^{-6} M$) in dichloromethane upon addition of (*S*)-2-amino-3-phenylpropan-1-ol (**4_S**) as the host : guest molar ratio changes from (A) 1 : 0 to 1 : 660 and (B) 1 : 700 to 1 : 4200 at 295 K.

Fig. 2. Isotopic distribution of the (A) theoretical and (B) experimental ESI-MS spectra of *sandwich-1•4_S* at 295 K.

Fig. 3. Job's plot establishing the 1 : 1 stoichiometry for the binding between **1** and (*S*)-2-amino-3-phenylpropan-1-ol (**4_S**) in dichloromethane at 295 K.

1 : 700 to 1 : 4200 of **4_S**, the spectral pattern again changes which include red shifts of the Soret band from 414 to 418 nm, a shoulder from 434 to 436 nm and Q-bands, respectively, from 557 to 560 and 601 to 602 nm as demonstrated in Fig. 1B. The spectrum thus obtained was very similar with the *anti* form of the 1 : 2 host-guest complex (Fig. 4A) obtained upon additions of excess (*S*)-2-butanol to **1** under identical condition. Single crystals of *anti*-

1•(4_S)₂ have been successfully grown and structurally characterized. There are two distinct concentration regions found in the process corresponding to the formation of the 1 : 1 *sandwich-1•4_S* and 1 : 2 *anti-1•(4_S)₂* species. Fig. 4B compares the UV-Vis spectra of **1**, 1 : 1 *sandwich-1•4_S* and 1 : 2 *anti-1•(4_S)₂*. Similar spectral observations are also obtained with other chiral guests where both 1 : 1 *sandwich* and 1 : 2 *anti* complexes are produced, respectively, at low and higher concentration of the guest ligands (Fig. S1). Single crystals of *anti-1•(6)*₂ have also been obtained and structurally characterized. Scheme 1 shows the synthetic outline of all the complexes reported here along with their abbreviations.

Fig. 4. UV-Visible spectra (selected portion only) in dichloromethane at 295 K of (A) 1 : 2 *anti-1•(4_S)₂* (dashed line) and **1•((S)-2-butanol)₂** (solid line) and (B) **1** (solid line), *sandwich-1•4_S* (dashed line) and *anti-1•(4_S)₂* (dotted line).

Crystallographic characterization :

Red crystals of the molecules are grown via slow diffusion of acetonitrile into chloroform solution of the complexes at room temperature. The complex *anti-1•(4_S)₂* crystallizes in the triclinic crystal system with *P*-1 space group while *anti-1•(6)*₂ in the monoclinic crystal system with *P*2₁/*n* space group (Tables 1 and 2). Molecular structures of the complexes are shown in Fig. 5 while the

selected bond distance and angles are given in Table 2. In both *anti-1•(4_S)₂* and *anti-1•(6)₂*, Mg^{II} centers have five coordinate square-pyramidal geometry and the metal ions are displaced by 0.44 and 0.37 Å, respectively, from the least-squares plane of the C₂₀N₄ porphyrinato core. The guest ligand binds to Mg^{II} centers through the OH group due to more binding affinity of magnesium ion towards oxygen. In *anti-1•(4_S)₂*, the average Mg-Np and Mg-O(L) distances are found to be 2.084(4) Å and 2.085(4) Å, respectively, while the corresponding distances are 2.077(2) and 2.053(2) Å for *anti-1•(6)₂*.

Fig. 5. Molecular structures (at 100 K) of (A) *anti-1•(4_S)₂* and (B) *anti-1•(6)₂*.

As can be seen, the chiral guest L binds only through the inside coordination in the 1 : 2 *anti* complex that is the necessary condition to generate chiroptical activity of the complex (*vide infra*). This is the first structural evidence of the chiroptical model that was proposed for 1 : 2 *anti* complex⁶. The phenyl group in *anti-1•(4_S)₂* has moved far due to such steric interactions with the ethyl group of the next porphyrin. Also, the axial ligand L in the *anti* complexes has been found to have orientation disorder.

Since no good quality of crystals were obtained that are suitable for structure determination for the 1 : 1 *sandwich* complexes, the molecules *sandwich-1•3_S* and *sandwich-1•3_R* were geometrically optimized using DFT (Fig. 6). As can be seen, the chiral amino alcohol can binds

comfortably with Mg^{II} centers within the bisporphyrin cavity as a 1 : 1 complex which results in a nonbonding Mg...Mg separation of 6.561 Å. Two porphyrin macrocycles are found to be twisted stereospecifically either in a clockwise or anticlockwise direction in order to minimize the host-guest steric interactions. It has been found that (*S*)-2-aminobutane-1-ol (**3_S**) shows clockwise twist of 65.35° while (*R*)-2-aminobutane-1-ol (**3_R**) displays an anticlockwise twist of -65.48°. Such a large twist angle is due to a very strong binding of the guest ligand within the host which results in large CD amplitude of the host-guest complex (*vide infra*).

Fig. 6. DFT optimized structure of *sandwich-1•3_S*.

Table 2. Selected bond distances (Å) and angles (°)

	<i>anti-1•(4_S)₂</i>	<i>anti-1•(6)₂</i>
Mg1-N1	2.079(4)	2.075(2)
Mg1-N2	2.096(3)	2.085(2)
Mg1-N3	2.084(4)	2.070(3)
Mg1-N4	2.079(3)	2.078(2)
Mg1-O1	2.085(4)	2.053(2)
N(1)-Mg1-N(2)	89.51(13)	89.33(10)
N(1)-Mg1-N(3)	160.96(15)	159.22(12)
N(1)-Mg1-N(4)	86.98(14)	86.62(9)
N(2)-Mg1-N(3)	86.74(14)	87.00(11)
N(2)-Mg1-N(4)	158.82(15)	160.31(11)
N(3)-Mg1-N(4)	89.81(14)	89.98(10)

¹H NMR spectral studies :

The ¹H NMR titration experiments were carried out at 295 K in CDCl₃. Fig. 7 shows the relevant spectra coming from the reaction between **1** and (*S*)-2-amino-3-phenylpropan-1-ol (**4_S**), as a representative example. Trace A shows the well-resolved ¹H NMR spectrum of **1** in CDCl₃ alone while trace B shows spectra after the addition of 1.0 molar equivalent of **4_S** which corresponds to *sandwich-1•4_S*. Trace C, however, presents the ¹H NMR of free **4_S**. The ¹H NMR spectral features of *sandwich* complex are large upfield shift of the guest ligand protons because of ligand's close proximity to two porphyrin subunits and hence strong ring current effect. This has resulted the upfield shift of ligand protons -CH, -CH₂ and NH₂ protons by Δδ 10.6, 8.8 and 10.8 ppm, respectively. In Mg^{II}-bisporphyrin, **1**, *meso*-10,20 protons are invisible due to the equilibrium between *syn* and *anti* forms. In the 1 : 1 complex three single peaks are observed for 10, 15 and 20 *meso* protons at 9.95, 9.45 and 9.65 ppm, respectively. On the other hand, bridging protons of the porphyrin subunits (-CH₂(b)) are splitted due to the twisting of

Fig. 7. ¹H NMR spectra in CDCl₃ at 295 K of (A) **1**, (B) *sandwich-1•4_S* and (C) free **4_S**.

the two porphyrins in the host-guest complex. Similar is the case with the other chiral guests also.

Circular dichroism (CD) :

The interaction of the chiral amino alcohol with **1** was monitored in solution using CD spectroscopy at 295 K. Upon addition of increasing amount of (*S*)-2-aminopropan-1-ol (**2_S**) to the dichloromethane solution of **1**, CD intensity gradually increases. CD amplitude becomes maximum (A_{obs} , +362 M⁻¹ cm⁻¹) upon additions of 2 equivalent of the chiral ligand. Further addition of the guest upto 890 equivalents causes no change in the CD intensity which implies formation of stable 1 : 1 *sandwich* complex; the spectral changes have been demonstrated in Fig. 8. However, after the addition of larger amount of guest (2200 equivalent), the 1 : 1 *sandwich* complex is converted to 1 : 2 *anti* complex with a decrease in CD intensity. In general, 1 : 1 *sandwich* complex incur stronger exciton coupling due to ditopic interactions between guest ligands and bisporphyrin. However, in the 1 : 2 host-guest complexes, the guest ligand that binds in one porphyrin ring, stereospecifically interact with the ethyl group of the

Fig. 8. CD spectral change of **1** (5×10^{-6} M) upon addition of (*S*)-2-aminopropan-1-ol (**2_S**) in dichloromethane as the host-guest molar ratio changes from (A) 1 : 0 to 1 : 890; (B) 1 : 900 to 1 : 2200 at 295 K.

neighbouring bisporphyrin, which eventually generate CD signal in solution but with less intensity compared to the 1 : 1 *sandwich* complex.

Similarly, upon addition of increasing amount of 3_R , 3_S , 4_S , 5_S separately to the dichloromethane solution of **1**, primarily 1 : 1 *sandwich* complex is produced with enhanced CD intensity, which subsequently decreases after addition of large amount of guest due to the formation of 1 : 2 *anti* complex (Figs. S2-S5). It has been observed that CD intensity in the 1 : 1 *sandwich* complex has been increased in the order $2_S < 3_R \sim 3_S < 4_S$ which is, however, the order of increasing bulk of the substituent at the chiral centre. However, the intensity of the CD signal (A_{obs} , $+90 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) substantially decreases for 5_S due to the presence of bulky phenyl group at the close proximity of binding site which increases substantial steric during ditopic 1 : 1 binding and thus weaken the binding constant (*vide infra*). Moreover, CD signal intensity is also similar but opposite in sign for a pair of enantiomeric guest ligands (Fig. 9).

Binding constant determination :

The binding constants between **1** and chiral amino alcohol L in solution are determined by CD spectroscopic titration methods using the HypSpec computer program (Protonic Software, UK)²⁰. Each Mg^{II} -bisporphyrin unit binds with the guest ligand in a 1 : 1 *sandwich* complex first which, upon increasing guest concentration, converts to 1 : 2 host-guest complex as shown in Scheme 1.

Two sets of CD titration data were analyzed consider-

Fig. 9. CD spectra (in dichloromethane at 295 K) of *sandwich-1•3_R* (dotted line) and *sandwich-1•3_S* (solid line).

ing two-step binding models for 1 : 1 *sandwich*, 1 : 2 host-guest complexes with binding constants of K_1 and K_2 , respectively. For complexation of **1** with 4_S , the values are found to be $6.8 \pm 0.1 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$ and $6.6 \pm 0.3 \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1}$, respectively (Fig. 10). Similarly, binding constants are determined for all other guests (Figs. S6-S9). It has been observed that with increasing the bulk of the substituent, the binding constant values for 1 : 1 *sandwich* complex decreases in the order $2_S < 3_R \sim 3_S < 4_S < 5_S$, which, however, is just opposite binding order for the 1 : 2 *anti* complex. Calculated CD spectral data and binding constants of the complexes are shown in Table 3.

Upon formation of a 1 : 1 *sandwich* complex through bidentate metal coordination of the chiral guest, chirality is transferred from the chiral guest to the achiral host introducing a preferential chiral twist in the porphyrin-

Fig. 10. (A) Calculated CD spectra for *sandwich-1•4_S* (solid line). (B) Fits of the titration data of **1** with 4_S to the theoretical binding isotherm data at selected wavelengths of 403 and 431 nm. (C) Species distribution plots in dichloromethane at 295 K.

Table 3. Calculated CD spectral data and binding constants of the complexes at 295 K

Guests	FC ^a		A _{cal} ^b (cm ⁻¹ M ⁻¹)	Binding constant K ₁ (M ⁻¹) ^c	SC ^a		Binding constant K ₂ (M ⁻¹) ^c
	1 : 1 complex, CD data λ (nm) [Δε, cm ⁻¹ M ⁻¹]				1 : 2 complex, CD data λ (nm) [sign]		
2 _S	431 [212]	402 [-150]	362	8.1 ± 0.2 × 10 ⁴	431[+]	402[-]	2.8 ± 0.3 × 10 ²
3 _R	430[-212]	401[180]	-392	7.6 ± 0.1 × 10 ⁴	430[-]	401[+]	5.0 ± 0.3 × 10 ³
3 _S	430[218]	401[-158]	376	7.2 ± 0.2 × 10 ⁴	430[+]	401[-]	6.2 ± 0.2 × 10 ³
4 _S	432[360]	402[-266]	626	6.8 ± 0.1 × 10 ⁴	432[+]	402[-]	6.6 ± 0.3 × 10 ³
5 _S	433[54]	403[-36]	90	1.6 ± 0.1 × 10 ⁴	433[+]	403[-]	8.2 ± 0.3 × 10 ³

^aFC : 1st Cotton effect; ^aSC : 2nd Cotton effect. ^bA : total amplitude in M⁻¹ cm⁻¹; A = |Δε₁ - Δε₂|. ^cCalculated from CD spectral measurement.

porphyrin arrangement which generates an exciton-coupled CD response. The sign of the Soret CD couplet is related to the absolute configuration of the substrate, while its intensity depends on several other factors. Ligands' pre-organized coordinating sites along with the differences in the effective size of the substituent around the chiral center of the ligand dictate the sign of interporphyrin helical twist. On examination of the Corey-Pauling-Koltun (CPK) molecular model shown in Fig. 11, it can be seen that the

two porphyrin units are twisted in an clockwise for *S*-type of chiral guest and anticlockwise direction for a *R*-type in order to minimum host-guest steric clash. Clockwise orientation of the two porphyrin unit results positive first Cotton effect while anticlockwise orientation results negative first Cotton effect of the CD couplet. CD spectra has been calculated for *sandwich-1•3_S* and *sandwich-1•3_R* using DFT whose sign have been found identical with the experiment also (Figs. 9 and 11).

Fig. 11. CPK molecular models and calculated CD spectra of (A) *sandwich-1•3_S* and (B) *sandwich-1•3_R*.

Upon further addition of guest, 1 : 1 *sandwich* complex is converted to the 1 : 2 *anti* complex. The sign of the CD signal of 1 : 2 *anti* complex with chiral amino alcohol reported here is, however, identical with the signals obtained using chiral mono alcohols such as (*S*)-2-butanol (Fig. 12). Due to the dynamic nature of the 1 : 2 host-guest systems, there are a number of possible conformations. However, there are two basic modes of binding for the guest ligands in *anti*-1•(L)₂: inside binding and outside binding (Fig. 13). In the case of inside binding, the ligation occurs from the side that results in a close spatial proximity to the ethyl groups of the adjacent porphyrin which leads to stereospecific twisting of the two bridged porphyrin units in order to minimize the host-guest steric clash. In sharp contrast, for outside binding of guest, these interactions are missing because of the distant location of the guests and hence would not show any chirality. As demonstrated here, chiral amino alcohol binds as ‘inside coordination’ and thereby interacts with the ethyl group of the neighbouring porphyrin unit stereospecifically

Fig. 12. CD and UV spectral change of **1** (5×10^{-6} M) upon addition of (*S*)-2-butanol in dichloromethane as the host-guest molar ratio changes from 1 : 0 to 1 : 450 at 295 K.

cally which, however, is necessary for supramolecular chirogenesis in the *anti* complex. Due to such a chirogenic event, a moderate exciton couplet CD signal is induced in the porphyrin Soret region.

Fig. 13. Schematic representation showing the importance of inside binding in the chirogenesis process in the 1 : 2 *anti* complex.

According to the CD exciton chirality method, the signs of the induced CD bands of the supramolecular systems are results of spatial orientation of the interacting electronic transition dipoles, as controlled by the absolute configuration of the chiral guest. In the case of the left-handed screw formed by (*R*)-ligands, the coupling B_{\parallel} transitions form an anticlockwise twist, while the coupling B_{\perp} transitions form a clockwise twist, which correspond to

the negative first and positive second Cotton effects (Fig. 14). The situation for right-handed screw by (*S*)-ligands is exactly opposite to that of the left-handed screw, giving positive first and negative second Cotton effects. Thus, the chirality sign correlates unequivocally with the generated helicity, allowing straightforward assignment of the guest's absolute configuration.

Fig. 14. Schematic diagram of the mechanism of chirality induction in achiral Mg^{II}-bisporphyrin, **1** upon interaction with chiral amino alcohol. The orientation of the Soret band electronic transitions in chiral complexes are shown in each of the molecule. Ethyl substituent and guest ligands have been omitted for clarity.

Conclusions

Ethane bridged Mg^{II}-bisporphyrin, **1** has been utilized as an effective achiral host to bind a series of amino alcohol as guest ligand L namely (*S*)-2-aminopropan-1-ol (**2_S**), (*R*)-2-aminobutan-1-ol (**3_R**), (*S*)-2-aminobutan-1-ol (**3_S**), (*S*)-2-amino-3-phenylpropan-1-ol (**4_S**), (*S*)-2-amino-2-phenylethanol (**5_S**) and 2-amino-2-methylpropan-1-ol (**6**). Stepwise addition of the chiral substrate initially produce 1 : 1 *sandwich* complex **1•L** at lower guest concentration which, upon further addition, converts to 1 : 2 *anti* complex **1•(L)₂**. Two-step changes in the UV-Vis spectra have also been observed during the titration of **1** with the guest ligand L. ESI-MS and Job's continuous variation plot confirm the formation of 1 : 1 *sandwich* complex at lower guest concentration. ¹H NMR spectra has revealed large upfield shifts of the guest protons because of the encapsulation of the guest within the bisporphyrin cavity in the *sandwich* complex.

Upon addition of the increasing amount of guest to the dichloromethane solution of **1**, CD amplitude becomes maximum due to the formation of 1 : 1 *sandwich* complex which is due to very strong binding of the guest ligand within the host. CD intensity in the 1 : 1 *sandwich* complex has been increased in the order **2_S** < **3_R** ~ **3_S** < **4_S** which is also the order of increasing bulk of the substituent at the chiral centre. However, the intensity of the CD signal substantially decreases for **5_S** due to the presence of bulky phenyl group at the close proximity of binding site which increases substantial steric with the bisporphyrin moiety during the ditopic 1 : 1 binding and thus weaken the binding constant. In the absence of the X-ray structure, 1 : 1 *sandwich* complex was geometrically optimized using DFT which displays a stereo-specific twist in order to minimize the host-guest steric clash. It has been found that (*S*)-2-aminobutane-1-ol (**3_S**) shows clockwise twist of 65.35° between two porphyrin rings while (*R*)-2-aminobutane-1-ol (**3_R**) displays an anticlockwise twist of -65.48° which results in the positive and negative sign, respectively, of the 1st Cotton effect of the CD couplet that are observed experimentally. The pre-existing chirality of the amino alcohol guests would make the two porphyrin macrocycles to be oriented in a clockwise direction

for *S*-type of chiral guest while anticlockwise for an *R*-type.

In presence of large excess of guest, the 1 : 1 *sandwich* complex converts to 1 : 2 *anti* complex with a decrease in CD intensity. X-Ray structure of *anti*-**1•(4_S)₂** and *anti*-**1•(6)₂** have been determined successfully in which amino alcohol binds to the Mg^{II}-center through the OH group due to stronger binding affinity towards oxygen atom. It has been observed that chiral guest L binds through the inside coordination in the 1 : 2 *anti* complex which is the necessary condition for the observed chiroptic response of the complex. The chiral guest ligand binds from the side that results in a close spatial proximity to the ethyl groups of the adjacent porphyrin leading to a stereo-specific twist between two bridged porphyrin units to produce chiroptic response. Thus, the chirality sign correlates unequivocally with the generated helicity, allowing straightforward assignment of the guest's absolute configuration.

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Supplementary materials

UV-Vis spectra, CD spectra and binding constants diagram of 1 : 1 *sandwich* and 1 : 2 *anti* complexes, CCDC-1438895 for *anti*-**1•(4_S)₂** and CCDC-1438896 for *anti*-**1•(6)₂** contains the supplementary crystallographic data for this paper. These data can be obtained free of charge from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre via www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/data_request/cif. Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version.

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